

Synthesis of Peptides of β -Amino-acids

A. B. Sen and M. S. Yajnik

Some new β -amino-acid peptides have been prepared from 1-(N - β -aminoacylpyrazoles) by the application of the method adopted by Ried *et al.*¹.

Ried *et al.*¹ have recently introduced a new method for the synthesis of peptides. In this method the amino-acid is converted into 1-(α -aminoacyl)pyrazole by the action of acetylacetone on the tosylated amino-acid hydrazide. The aminoacylpyrazole is then condensed with amino-acid esters in a basic medium, such as triethylamine, with the formation of a tosylated peptide. The amino-group end of the ester acts on the N-CO bond of the pyrazole in such a way that the bond between N and CO breaks and the -CO- combines with the NH_2 group of the ester to furnish a tosylated peptide:

In the present communication this method has been applied for the synthesis of peptides of β -aminobutyric acid, β -alanine, β -amino- β -phenylpropionic acid and also glycine with these amino-acid esters.

EXPERIMENTAL

*Esters of β -Amino-acids*²—Thionyl chloride (0.1*M*, 9 ml) was added dropwise under stirring to ethanol (50 ml), cooled to 5°, followed by the amino-acid (0.1*M*). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. on a water bath and then the excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure. The amino-acid ester hydrochloride was precipita-

1. *Annalen*, 1958, **619**, 43.

2. Boissonnas *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **39**, 1421.

ted with ethanol-ether mixture. The free ester was obtained by passing a slow stream of dry ammonia in a suspension of the ester in chloroform.

The tosyl derivatives of the amino-acid esters were obtained by following the method of Karrer and Van.⁹

β-Amino-acid Hydrazide.—The tosylated amino-acid ester (0.1*M*), hydrazine hydrate (0.2*M*), and anhydrous ethanol (100 ml) were refluxed for 3 hr. The hydrazide was isolated in the usual way and purified by recrystallisation from methanol. The m.p., yields, and analyses of the hydrazides are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

R.	M.P.	Formula.	%Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
H	150°	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S	80	16.25	16.30
Me	160°	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	76	15.29	15.30
Ph	148°	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	85	12.50	12.60

1 - (*N-Tosyl - β-aminoacyl - 3,5 - dimethylpyrazole*). — *N-Tosylamino-acid hydrazide* (0.065*M*), acetylacetone (0.07*M*), and anhydrous ethanol (70 ml) were refluxed for 3 hr. on a water bath. The crystals of the pyrazole separating on cooling were filtered and recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The yields, m.p., and analyses of these compounds are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

R.	M.P.	Formula.	%Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
H	94°	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	85	12.94	13.00
Me	110°	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃ S	80	12.60	12.60
Ph	120°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	79	7.00	7.05

Tosyl Derivatives of Peptides of β-Amino-acids.—*β-Aminoacylpyrazole* (0.02*M*) and the requisite *β-amino-acid ester* (0.023*M*) were mixed and the mixture was heated on a boiling water bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the excess of amino-acid ester was removed on a water bath under reduced pressure. The residue was poured in

TABLE III

R-CO-NHR'.

No.	R.	R'.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	*Rf.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		%Nitrogen.	
							Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	M-CH ₂ -CH ₂	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOEt	65°	80	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.80	52.51	52.53	6.31	6.43	8.05	8.10
2	"	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOEt	70°	70	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.80	53.78	53.90	6.52	6.74	7.75	7.80
3	"	Me -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOEt	84°	65	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.80	60.13	60.28	6.10	6.22	6.03	6.66
4	"	Ph -CH ₂ -COOEt	107°	67	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.50	51.10	51.21	6.04	6.09	8.44	8.50
5	M-CH-CH ₂	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOEt	60°	63	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.68	53.78	53.90	6.58	6.74	7.76	7.80
6	"	Me -CH-CH ₂ -COOEt	78°	84	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.70	55.08	55.13	7.01	7.02	7.55	7.52
7	"	Ph -CH-CH ₂ -COOEt	85°	86	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.53	61.01	61.11	6.61	6.71	6.04	6.10
8	"	-CH ₂ -COOEt	60°	74	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.47	..	..	..	..	8.1	8.10
9	M-CH-CH ₂	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOEt	90°	69	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.40	..	..	..	..	6.50	6.66
10	"	Ph -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOEt	82°	56	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.06	..	..	..	..	6.00	6.10
11	"	Me -CH-CH ₂ -COOEt	82°	56	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.26	..	..	..	..	5.70	5.80
12	"	Ph -CH ₂ -COOEt	67°	61	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.40	..	..	..	..	6.42	6.60
13	M-CH ₂ -	-CH-CH ₂ -COOEt	71°	58	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.55	..	..	..	..	8.00	8.10
14	"	Me -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COOEt	55°	67	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.62	..	..	..	..	8.43	8.60
15	"	Ph -CH-CH ₂ -COOEt	80°	71	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	0.56	..	..	..	..	6.56	6.60

*For Rf values the chromatograms were run in n-butanol: acetic acid: water (4:1:5).

water and the oily layer was extracted with ether. The extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether distilled. The residue was recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The m.p., yields, R_f values, and analyses of the compounds are recorded in Table III.

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